

ETHYL BIODIESEL SIMULATION: EVALUATION OF KINETIC AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Guilherme Ramalho Mendes¹, Ana Maria dos Santos Magalhães², Lilian Caroline Kramer Biasi^{3,4}, Guilherme José Máximo², Marcela Cravo Ferreira¹

¹ University of Campinas, School of Technology

² University of Campinas, School of Food Engineering, Department of Food Engineering and Technology

³ University of Campinas, School of Chemical Engineering, Department of Chemical Systems Engineering

⁴ University of São Paulo, Engineering School, Department of Chemical Engineering

Contact email: marcela@ft.unicamp.br

ABSTRACT – Concerns about environmental impacts have driven the development of innovations to mitigate impacts and generate more sustainable energy sources. The two main liquid biofuels used in Brazil are ethanol and, on an increasing scale, biodiesel. The industrial method used for biodiesel production is transesterification using sodium hydroxide and methanol, which keeps the process limited to the availability of fossil input. The replacement of methanol for more sustainable solvents has been the subject of several studies, in this contest ethanol represents a relevant alternative. Furthermore, complications in the biofuel purification stage and waste generation are some of the technical and environmental problems that the transesterification using sodium hydroxide as a catalyst can generate. Enzymatic transesterification is an innovative process and an advantageous alternative to the traditional alkaline homogeneous transesterification process, since the enzyme is biodegradable and reusable, which responds to a current demand for more sustainable processes. The use of simulators allows the comparison and evaluation of different routes of biodiesel production, but the success of computer simulation is based on reliable physical properties and process parameters. Thus, the goal of this study is to investigate the thermodynamic and kinetic parameters for the ethyl biodiesel simulation by the alkaline homogeneous and enzymatic routes using COCO (Cape-Open to CapeOpen) simulator. Firstly, the fatty compounds database was built, where oil was represented by the triacylglycerol trilinolein. Vapor pressure values for the fatty compounds based on literature data were implemented in the simulator. Three sets of parameters of the UNIFAC model were used for the analysis of the liquid-liquid equilibrium (LLE) prediction for the system present in the biodiesel separation step. The parameter set from literature for multicomponent biodiesel systems exhibited satisfactory performance in estimating the LLE data with the

lowest global mean deviation (2.9 %). The kinetic parameters from literature for the homogeneous alkaline and enzymatic transesterification with ethanol were used in the simulation of ethylic biodiesel and a good agreement between experimental and simulated results was achieved. Finally, a simulation was performed contemplating the reaction and separation steps for both the alkaline and enzymatic production routes. From this analysis, it was possible to identify the differences related to the process design and the products obtained.

Keywords: Biodiesel, Simulation, ELL, Kinetic.

1. INTRODUCTION

Increases in demand for biofuel production, stimulated by concerns about environmental impacts, have encouraged the use of vegetable oils for biofuel production. Recently, in Brazil, after bioethanol, biodiesel is the most widely used biofuel. In response to this increase in biodiesel production, many strategies regarding catalytic processes and raw materials are increasingly speculated, aiming to optimize its production and minimize the environmental impacts.

Industrially, the most used method for biodiesel production is the chemical transesterification of vegetable oils with methanol, using sodium hydroxide as a catalyst [1]. The high conversion rates of triacylglycerols (TAG) to esters is one of the advantages of homogeneous alkaline catalysis. However, the contents of free fatty acids and water present in the raw material, negatively influence the process: catalyst is consumed, forming “soap”, thus, increasing the viscosity of the final product and hampering the glycerol separation [2]. Alternatively, enzymatic catalysis is a promising technique that helps mitigate operational problems and is a technological option that meets the current demand for cleaner and more selective processes [3].

The methyl route is the most viable production route, due to methanol reactivity, low cost, and easy alcohol recovery, as well as simpler purification of biodiesel. However, the non-renewable character of methanol and the Brazilian availability of bioethanol encourage the development of another production route in the country. The economic viability of the production of ethyl biodiesel would be facilitated if the biodiesel plant is integrated with ethanol, in a biorefinery conception [4].

Computational simulation is a tool that allows the comparison of new production alternatives, which is important to evaluate the feasibility of the process and the equipment

dimensions. In the case of biodiesel production, it is essential to provide physical properties and process parameters information. Thus, this work aimed to investigate the thermodynamic and kinetic parameters for the ethyl biodiesel simulation by the alkaline homogeneous and enzymatic routes using COCO (Cape-Open to CapeOpen) simulator.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

As a first step, the substances involved in the production of ethyl biodiesel were included in the COCO (Cape-Open to CapeOpen) simulator, since the simulator does not have these substances in its database. In Brazil, the main raw material to produce biodiesel is soybean oil, which has linoleic acid as its main fatty acid. Thus, for the oil composition, the trilinolein molecule was used as the representative triacylglycerol. To evaluate the entire reaction process of biodiesel production, the molecules dilinolein, monolinolein, and ethyl linoleate were also included. For a better representation of the simulation, the Antoine equation coefficients for the calculation of vapor pressure for lipid compounds described by Ndiaye et al. (2005) [5] were also implemented.

2.1. Liquid-Liquid Equilibrium

The UNIFAC group contribution thermodynamic model was applied to estimate the liquid-liquid equilibrium at all steps of the simulation. The experimental data determined by Ferreira et al. [6] for the soybean ethyl biodiesel system were compared with those estimated by the UNIFAC model using a liquid-liquid flash. Three sets of UNIFAC model parameters were analyzed: the original parameters determined by Magnussen et al. [7] (named 'Original'); the ones adjusted by Bessa et al. [8] (named 'Bessa') for systems involved in biodiesel production; and the parameters estimated by Hirata et al. [9] (named 'Hirata') for systems involved in vegetable oil refining. The calculation of the overall mean deviation between the experimental and calculated data was performed according to Equation 1.

$$\Delta w = 100 \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^K [(w_{i,n}^{BP,exp} - w_{i,n}^{BP,calc})^2 + (w_{i,n}^{GP,exp} - w_{i,n}^{GP,calc})^2]}{2NK}} \quad (1)$$

where N and K are the number of tie-lines and components, BP and GP are related to the Biodiesel- and Glycerol-rich phases, exp and $calc$ refer to the experimental and calculated mass fractions (w), respectively.

2.2. Kinetic parameters of the transesterification reaction

The kinetics of ethyl biodiesel via alkaline and enzymatic transesterification were

simulated by implementing several continuous cascade reactors to represent a batch reaction. The results were compared with literature data. For alkaline transesterification, NaOH was used as the catalyst at 35°C in a CSRT reactor, configured with the kinetic constants reported by Dias [10]. The same procedure was performed to verify the kinetics of ethyl biodiesel via enzymatic transesterification, using the kinetic constants based on data from Magalhaes [11] for enzymatic catalysis with enzyme concentration of 5% at 50°C.

2.3. Process Simulation

Figure 1 shows the biodiesel production flowsheet simulated based on the process proposed by Knothe et al. [1]. A configuration containing a CSTR reactor, the first decanter for glycerol separation, a distillation column for ethanol recovery, and a decanter for the washing step was proposed. The feed was 100 kg/h with an ethanol/oil molar ratio of 9:1. For the alkaline transesterification, the kinetic parameters from Dias [10] were used in a CSTR reactor and for the enzymatic transesterification, a CSTR reactor was considered with the kinetic parameters based on data from Magalhaes [11]. The distillation column was configured to maximize ethanol recovery at the top and minimize biodiesel loss. The Gamma-Phi thermodynamic model with the original UNIFAC vapor-liquid parameters was used. In the decanters, the UNIFAC thermodynamic model with liquid-liquid parameters was used with the parameter set described by Bessa et al. [8] and with a temperature of 25°C.

Figure 1. Flowsheet of biodiesel production simulated in COCO.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Liquid-Liquid Equilibrium

Figure 2 shows the experimental data for the liquid-liquid equilibrium system during the biodiesel reaction step determined by Ferreira et al. [6] and the data predicted by the UNIFAC models with the three different parameter sets. The overall average deviation between experimental and calculated data was 5.1%, 2.9%, and 4.4%, for the original UNIFAC parameter sets, Bessa and Hirata, respectively. The parameters readjusted by Bessa et al. [8] improved the prediction of the liquid-liquid equilibrium compared to the original parameters, indicating that this set of parameters is appropriate for predicting the liquid-liquid equilibrium for ethylic biodiesel systems.

Figure 2. Liquid-liquid equilibrium of TAG + DAG + MAG + Fatty Acid + Ethyl Biodiesel + Glycerol + Ethanol at 30°C: experimental data (Ferreira et al. [6]) and predicted by the UNIFAC model.

3.2. Kinetic parameters of the transesterification reaction

The results of the comparison between the experimental and simulated data for alkaline and enzymatic transesterification can be seen in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. It is possible to verify the conformity between the data calculated by the simulator and the data from the literature. It is possible to observe the difference in reaction time between the catalytic

processes by alkaline transesterification (Figure 3) and by enzymatic catalysis (Figure 4). For enzymatic catalysis a longer residence time is required to achieve higher ethyl esters conversion rates. The root mean square deviation between the experimental and calculated molar fractions was 0.76% and 4.2% for alkaline and enzymatic transesterifications, respectively, indicating that the sets of constants are suitable for describing reaction kinetics.

Figure 3. Alkaline catalysis simulation with constant of Dias [10]: simulated result (lines); experimental results (●: Trilinolein and ●: ethyl linoleate).

Figure 4. Enzymatic catalysis simulation with constant of Magalhaes [11]: simulated result (lines); experimental results (●: Trilinolein and ●: ethyl linoleate).

3.3. Process Simulation

The configuration shown in Figure 1 was simulated and the results for alkaline and enzymatic transesterification are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. It was possible to achieve a high purity of ethyl linoleate in the biodiesel stream for both routes. For both

catalytic routes evaluated, it was possible to verify from the first decanter the separation of the glycerol phase, then it was possible to recover the excess ethanol in the distillation column, and finally, the excess glycerol was removed from the biodiesel stream by the washing step in the second decanter. No significant differences were observed in the configurations of the distillation column and the decanters.

Table 1. Composition of the simulation streams for the production of ethyl biodiesel by the alkaline route.

Mass percentage (%)	Stream					
	Feed	Reactor output	Biodiesel phase	Glycerol phase	Column Bottom output	Biodiesel
Trilinolein	67.00	0.29	0.34	0.00	0.42	0.43
Dilinolein	0.00	1.27	1.52	0.02	1.88	1.88
Monolinolein	0.00	1.60	1.71	1.07	2.11	2.11
Glycerol	0.00	6.38	0.95	32.91	1.17	0.03
Ethanol	33.00	22.91	14.96	61.77	0.00	0.00
Water	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.06
Ethyl linoleate	0.00	67.55	80.51	4.23	94.41	94.49

Table 2. Composition of the simulation streams for the production of ethyl biodiesel by the enzymatic route.

Mass percentage (%)	Stream					
	Feed	Reactor output	Biodiesel phase	Glycerol phase	Column Bottom output	Biodiesel
Trilinolein	67.00	1.19	1.45	0.00	1.77	1.77
Dilinolein	0.00	0.39	0.47	0.00	0.58	0.58
Monolinolein	0.00	0.17	0.18	0.11	0.22	0.22
Glycerol	0.00	6.79	0.85	34.03	1.04	0.02
Ethanol	33.00	22.74	14.20	61.91	0.00	0.00
Water	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.02
Ethyl linoleate	0.00	68.73	82.85	3.94	96.39	96.39

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results for the liquid-liquid equilibrium analysis show that the set of UNIFAC parameters Bessa et al. [8] was the most suitable for the biodiesel systems. The low root mean

square deviation obtained from the analysis simulation of the kinetics showed the suitability of using the literature constants for the representation of kinetics for alkaline and enzymatic transesterifications. The simulations of the biodiesel production process showed to be possible the obtainment of high purity ethyl biodiesel through both routes.

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6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (Finance Code 001) and Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (process numbers 2021/09028-1, 2016/18253-0, 2014/21252-0) for the financial support.